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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛЕКСИКИ, ВНЕСЕННЫЕ ИММИГРАНТАМИ

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Аннотация: Систематическая классификация и тематическая классификация эмиграции, этимологический анализ, источники и методы формирования средневековой британской лексикографии комплексно не изучались. Особый интерес представляет изучение мультикультурных терминов, которые встречаются у иммигрантов.

Ключевые слова: мультикультурализм, заимствование слова, иммигранты, язык, вариативность.

LINGUO-CULTURAL ASPECTS OF VOCABULARY COMING WITH IMMIGRANTS

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Abstract: The systematic classification and thematic classification of emigration, etymological analysis, sources and methods of formation of medieval British lexicography have not been studied in complexly. It is of particular interest to study the multicultural terms that come with immigrants, drawing on various facts.

Key words: multiculturalism, borrowings, immigrants, language, variation.

Language and culture are closely related. Each language is related to a certain group of people. This means that when you are in contact with any language, you are in a complete relationship with the culture the language belongs to. Without language, it is impossible to understand any culture.

Learning or teaching any language is not just learning its alphabet, grammatical rules, sentence structure. While learning or teaching a language, we learn the traditions and way of life of the society to which the language belongs. All those factors together make up the language. Language can not exist without the culture, way of life and traditions of the society to which it belongs. Multiculturalism and language complement each other.

One of the most important issues of the education system faces today while studying the foreign language is teaching the culture, traditions and history of the nation. This is the very point when the linguo-culture and linguo-country-study can help us. As you can see from the term linguo-culture studies the relation between the language and culture, it uncovers the circle of their influence on each other and shows the ways of their enrichment. The linguo-country-study investigates the language units that clearly express the cultural features of each nation. Both fields of science address a number of important issues, such as the lexical development of language units, the historical development of changes in the semantics of language units, the role of multicultural terms in the language system and the study of differences in the lexical development of language units.

Considering the above mentioned factors it becomes clear that without knowing history and culture it's impossible to teach and to learn any language. At the same time, it is more interesting to approach the teaching of a foreign language from a cultural point of view; it helps to master the language fully.

The term *linguo-culturology* was introduced to the linguistic world in the end of the XX century. This term was used for the first time in the works of V.N.Telia's Phraseological school, V.V.Vorobyova, V.A.Maslova and others.

While teaching bilingual words linguo-culturology and linguo-country-study helps us to explain the meaning of these words. It's impossible to translate the bilingual words. Bilingual words are closely related to the history and culture of the language. While teaching these words we can only explain their meanings. Let's take a look at the word *Chapel* 'non English church' (from old French *chapele*, from medieval latin *capella*) and it was used in the opposite meaning of *Church of England*. In Britain the people who visited *chapel* were considered the lower class.

For example when we hear the phrase *the boxing day* we think that this phrase is closely related to the sport. However, it is clear from the analysis that this expression is closely connected with the customs of the Normandian tribes. During the middle Ages, when the Normans attacked Britain, they put a box on the harbor and always threw money into it. However the British have made the slightest change in the meaning of this expression. So, each year at Christmas, on December 25, they gave boxes with money, food or clothing to those who needed it. I would like to note that this tradition was later adopted by USA, Ireland, Scotland and other countries.

The word *honeymoon* is of Anglo-Saxon origin. In middle ages in Britain the father of bride had to provide the groom with honey drink within a month. Nowadays the meaning of this word had slightly changed. Now when we say *honeymoon* we mean a holiday spent together by newly married couple.

It should be noted that when the borrowings entered the language in a group form, not only simple and new words occur in the lexicon of the language but we can also observe the complex units that were morphologically composed. As a result a group of new words were derived from borrowed and native words. Thus, the morphology and vocabulary of the language was significantly expanded.

We can observe the close relation of language and multiculturalism in proverbs, phraseological units and idioms. Proverbs and idioms reflect the unique features of the language they belong to. They express the history, the culture, the traditions and the way of life the people to which the language belongs. So, while teaching idioms, proverbs and phraseological units linguo-culture helps teachers to explain them. Let's take a look at the example:

A cat may look at a king – even a person of low status has rights;

To have one's cake and eat it - you cannot simultaneously retain your cake and eat it.

Examples for phraseological units:

To ride in the marrow – bone coach – is used in the meaning of 'to go on foot'. These proverbs, idioms and phraseological units take their roots from middle ages.

I would like to note that this language variability is closely connected with multicultural Britain in Middle Ages. For some reasons immigrants from different countries came to Britain and settled there. The lexicon brought by immigrants had made evolution of language variability inevitable. We can easily find out lots of information which prove invariability is the basis of variability. According to A.I.Molotkova variability is one of the main features of phraseology. So, it should be noted that the component of phraseology loses some features related with word [3, p.63].

According to David Adger a little unit by keeping the meaning characteristic can have several different shapes [4, p.8].

The author gives several examples where he shows the use of auxiliary verbs in different dialects.

a. You have na a wrinkle

You don't have a single wrinkle

b. Aye, you do na have the champagne in there

Yes, you don't have the champagne in here [4, s.6].

Let's take a look at the author's types of sentences worked in another version:

a. I wisna sick or nothin, ye ken

I wasn't sick or anything, you know

b. Never heard of a woman director or onythin.

I'd never heard of a woman director or anything [4, s.7]

So, these examples again prove the role of variability in the system of language.

In the process of study we see that different linguistics approach to variation in different ways. In most cases, they say that variations in language mean changes in language over time. It is understood as a function of some kind of language.

On this occasion S.E. Malov writes: "The point is that the language and its roots are similar in structure" [2, p.59]. He notes that the structure of the language may be identical to its root structure, or vice versa, which may have been slightly or very deformed.

The active integration of various dialects into the medieval British lexicon accelerated this process, and we would even say that it was characterized by interference in the phonetic-lexical-semantic-grammatical levels of the language.

Summarizing the above mention we can conclude that the lexical richness of the English language in the middle ages played an irreplaceable role in the formation of British multiculturalism and enriched it. From this point of view it should be considered important to teach linguo-cultural units while teaching English as foreign language. No one can master language without knowing its history and language.

Thus, the protection of multicultural values is a requirement of time. It is impossible to define the formation of medieval British multiculturalism without analyzing the medieval linguistic diversity, without examining its origins, causes, methods, and ways.

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